
Implementation of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency in 2023

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ABSTRACT

The Desa Cantik or Cinta Statistik Program was initiated to strengthen village-level statistical capacity and support evidence-based development planning in Indonesia. However, variations in implementation across villages indicate the need for a deeper analysis of how the program is carried out at the local level. This study aims to analyze the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency by examining factors that influence its effectiveness. The research employed a descriptive qualitative approach and was conducted in Sumberrejo Village, Balen Village, and Dander Village, which were purposively selected as program implementers with differing capacities in data management. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, observation, and document analysis, and analyzed using the interactive model proposed by Miles et al. The analysis was guided by Edward III policy implementation framework, which includes communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The findings indicate that the program has been generally well implemented, supported by clear communication mechanisms, committed implementers, adequate institutional structures, and structured coordination among stakeholders. Nevertheless, challenges remain related to human resource capacity, consistency of inter-institutional coordination, data quality assurance, and the utilization of evaluation results. Overall, the Desa Cantik Program has contributed positively to improving village data governance in Bojonegoro Regency, although further strengthening is required to ensure sustainability and maximize its impact on development planning.

KEYWORDS: Desa Cantik Program, Policy Implementation, Village Data, Village, Governance

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1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly digitized global context, data and information management has become an important foundation in supporting sustainable development. Accurate, up-to-date, and relevant data not only serve as a basis for planning but also as an instrument for evaluation and public policy decision-making (Čelik-Memić et al., 2025; Husna, 2025; Marie et al., 2024; Puspitasari, 2024). The United Nations (2021) emphasizes that effective use of data can increase transparency and government accountability, as well as encourage public participation in the development process. Countries with effective data governance systems have proven to be able to formulate more targeted social policies, as demonstrated by the Scandinavian countries, which have achieved high levels of public welfare through data-based policies (OECD, 2020). Conversely, weak data management often results in ineffective development programs.

In line with this global trend, Indonesia has made strengthening data governance one of its national development priorities. Law No. 6 of 2014 on Villages affirms the position of villages as subjects of development with authority over planning and implementing development based on local needs. Within this framework, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) launched the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) as a strategic effort to improve the capacity of village officials in managing and utilizing statistical data optimally. This program aims to encourage evidence-based village development through increased statistical literacy and strengthening of village data systems (Isnaini & Khikmah, 2025; Mariani & Wicaksono, 2023; Septini & Suriadi, 2025).

Bojonegoro Regency is one of the regions actively implementing the Desa Cantik Program. Based on BPS data, Bojonegoro Regency has 419 villages spread across 28 sub-districts with diverse social and economic characteristics. In 2022, the population of Bojonegoro reached approximately 1,343,164, with 153,400 of them still classified as poor. This condition shows that poverty and welfare inequality are still serious challenges. On the other hand, Bojonegoro has great natural resource potential, especially in the

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agriculture and energy sectors, but its utilization has not been fully optimized due to limited access to information, data literacy, and technology at the village level.

The implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency began in 2021 with the designation of Prayungan Village and Kauman Village as national pilot villages. The program was then gradually expanded until 2024 to include a number of villages in various subdistricts. Each stage of implementation emphasized strengthening the capacity of village officials in data management, statistical analysis, digitization of village information, and increasing community participation in the compilation and utilization of development data. In general, this program has made a positive contribution to improving statistical literacy and awareness among village officials of the importance of data as a basis for development planning (BPS, 2024).

However, the implementation of the Desa Cinta Statistik Program in Bojonegoro Regency still faces various challenges. The imbalance in the capacity of village human resources, limitations in information technology infrastructure, and suboptimal coordination and communication between stakeholders are the main obstacles. In addition, changes in village status—such as an increase in the number of independent villages but a decrease in advanced villages—raise questions about the effectiveness of statistical data utilization in promoting sustainable village development. Community participation, which tends to be formalistic, and a low understanding of the function of statistical data also indicate that statistical literacy at the grassroots level still needs to be strengthened (Akbar & Wijaya, 2024; Doloji, 2025; Sumargo et al., 2025).

Previous studies have shown that the success of the Desa Cinta Statistik (Desa Cantik) program is largely determined by improvements in the statistical literacy of village officials and communities, ongoing assistance, and the use of data in development planning. Fisabilillah & Setiawan (2025) emphasize that the development of Desa Cantik in Bumiayu Village does not only focus on the technical aspects of data processing, but also on strengthening the capacity of village officials to be able to independently manage and utilize statistical data in supporting village development. In line with this, Kusuma & Khoiri (2024) emphasize that the introduction of Desa Cantik plays a strategic role in encouraging more accurate, targeted, and participatory data-based village development planning. Meanwhile, Dalimunthe et al. (2023) show that improving statistical literacy through socialization and assistance activities for the community can strengthen residents' understanding of the importance of data, while also increasing community participation in the data collection and decision-making processes at the local level. However, these three studies still emphasize aspects of guidance, socialization, and technical capacity building, so that studies on the comprehensive implementation of the Desa Cantik Program from the perspective of public policy implementation theory are still relatively limited and require further exploration.

Based on these conditions, this study aims to analyze the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency using Edward III's (1980) policy implementation theory framework, which includes the dimensions of communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. This study is expected to provide an empirical description of the dynamics of program implementation at the local level, identify factors that support and hinder implementation, and formulate strategic recommendations for local governments and stakeholders in optimizing data-based village development. Therefore, this study is titled "Implementation of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency in 2023."

2. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to analyze the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency. This approach was chosen because it allows researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of the program implementation process, interactions between actors, and the experiences and perceptions of implementers and village communities (Creswell, 2018; Sugiyono, 2019). The research analysis is based on Edward's III (1980) policy implementation theory, which includes indicators of communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure.

The research was conducted in Sumberrejo Village, Balen Village, and Dander Village, which were selected purposively because they are villages implementing the Desa Cantik Program and represent variations in village statistical data management capacity. Research informants were determined using purposive sampling, considering the informants' direct involvement and knowledge of program implementation (Sugiyono, 2022).

Table 1. Research Informants

Informant Group	Number	Description
Village Head	3	Heads of Sumberrejo, Balen, and Dander Villages
Village Officials	6	Village website managers, village secretaries, and administrative staff
BPS Bojonegoro Regency	2	BPS officers involved in the Desa Cantik Program
Village Community Members	10	Village residents who are beneficiaries or users of Desa Cantik data

Source: Data processed by researchers (2025)

The research data consisted of primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through in-depth interviews with key informants and direct observation of program implementation in the villages. Secondary data was collected through

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documentation studies, including BPS reports, local government documents, and other supporting documents relevant to the Desa Cantik Program.

Data analysis was conducted using the interactive analysis model from Miles et al. (2014), which includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing and verification. Data validity was maintained through source and method triangulation, by comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation to ensure the consistency and credibility of the research findings.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Communication

Within the framework of George C. Edwards' (1980) policy implementation theory, communication is a key indicator that determines the success of policy implementation. Effective communication requires clarity of message, consistency of information, and the ability of policy implementers to translate program objectives into concrete actions. In the context of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency, communication serves as the main foundation for village officials and the community to understand and optimally implement the program's objectives, benefits, and mechanisms.

a. Program Mechanism

The results of the study show that the communication mechanism of the Desa Cantik Program is implemented through various forms of socialization, including technical training for village officials, dissemination of information to the community, and the use of digital and traditional media. Based on secondary data from the BPS of Bojonegoro Regency (2023) and Bojonegoro Regency planning document for 2024, program socialization is carried out in stages and repeatedly to strengthen the understanding of program implementers and targets.

Training and workshops for village officials are the main mechanisms for disseminating program information. These activities focus on village statistical data management, the use of digital data collection applications, and understanding data-driven development. Training is conducted at least two to three times a year in each implementing village, with the aim of building the capacity of village officials to manage data consistently and sustainably. In addition, socialization to the community is carried out through village meetings, community deliberations, and group forums such as PKK and farmer groups, with an emphasis on the importance of community participation in the process of collecting and utilizing statistical data.

The use of communication media also shows a variety of approaches. Face-to-face media remains the primary method because it is considered effective in encouraging direct interaction and two-way discussion. On the other hand, the use of WhatsApp groups for village officials, village websites, brochures, and neighborhood announcements has been intensified to expand the reach of information and accelerate the flow of communication, especially for the productive age group.

The frequency of the Desa Cantik Program outreach in 2023 in the three research villages can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Frequency of the Desa Cantik Program Outreach in 2023

Village	Frequency of Socialization	Average Number of Participants	Main Socialization Media
Sumberrejo	3 times	42 people	Face-to-face, Zoom
Balen	2 times	38 people	Face-to-face, Zoom
Dander	3 times	35 people	Face-to-face, Zoom

Source: BPS Bojonegoro Regency (2023)

The table shows that Sumberrejo Village has the highest frequency of socialization, both in terms of the number of activities and the number of participants. This condition is in line with the role of Sumberrejo Village as the district center, which requires a higher intensity of assistance compared to other villages.

These findings are reinforced by the results of interviews with village officials and the community. Sumberrejo Village officials stated:

"Socialization from BPS is usually carried out three times a year. The main activities are held at the village hall with materials explaining how to collect statistical data and the importance of data in development. However, for those of us who are not familiar with statistics, the material is sometimes still difficult to digest."

Meanwhile, the Balen Village Data Management Team revealed that although the training provided was quite helpful, its frequency was still considered limited:

"The training we received was quite helpful, especially the one discussing digital data collection applications. But the frequency is still limited, so after the training we have to learn from each other in the village."

From the community's perspective, members of the Sumberrejo Village PKK highlighted the obstacle of understanding technical terms in the socialization, but this was offset by informal support from village officials and the younger generation:

“Sometimes we don’t understand the technical terms used in the socialization. But the young people and village officials usually help translate. We also get information through a WhatsApp group that was created specifically for this purpose.”

Overall, the results of the study show that the socialization mechanism for the Desa Cantik Program has been running regularly and involves various actors, both village officials and the community. The frequency and level of participation are positive indicators that the program has received sufficient attention at the village level. However, there are still obstacles in adjusting the socialization material to the level of understanding of the participants. Technical materials tend to be difficult for some village officials and community members, especially those with low educational backgrounds and the elderly.

This finding is in line with Smith et al. (2022), who emphasizes that the effectiveness of policy communication is greatly influenced by the ability of policy communicators to adapt messages to the social and cultural context and the capacity of the policy targets. Therefore, even though the communication mechanisms of the Desa Cantik Program have fulfilled the elements of clarity and consistency, optimization of methods and simplification of socialization materials are still needed so that program information can be understood evenly by all levels of society.

b. Information Flow and Coordination

In Edward's III (1980) theory of policy implementation, information flow and coordination are crucial elements in communication indicators. Edward emphasizes that policies can only be implemented effectively if information, instructions, and policy messages flow clearly, timely, and in a coordinated manner between levels of bureaucracy. Structured communication channels enable policy implementers at the lower levels to understand the intent of the policy as formulated by policymakers.

In the context of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency, the flow of information and coordination is a decisive factor in the success of program implementation. This program involves many actors across institutions, ranging from the Bojonegoro Regency BPS as the initiator, the regency government, districts, to village governments and communities. Therefore, the effectiveness of communication is highly dependent on the integration of coordination at every level of government.

Based on official documents from the Bojonegoro Regency Government and BPS (2023–2025), the information flow mechanism for the Desa Cantik Program begins with the Bojonegoro Regency BPS, which acts as the initiator and main person in charge of the program. BPS formulates technical policies, implementation guidelines, and conveys program information to relevant regional agencies such as Diskominfo and Bappeda, as well as to districts as extensions at the regional level.

Districts have a strategic role as a link between BPS and village governments. Districts are responsible for conveying technical information, coordinating socialization and training schedules, and facilitating technical assistance to villages. Furthermore, at the village level, the village head, village secretary, and village data team are tasked with managing the process of collecting, validating, processing, and reporting statistical data through the designated village information system and digital applications.

This information flow and coordination structure is supported by various communication media. The district BPS utilizes coordination meetings, official letters, and digital applications for supervision and assistance. The Communication and Information Agency and the Regional Development Planning Agency play a role in supporting technical aspects and facilitating communication through meetings and digital platforms. The district uses coordination meetings and field assistance as the main media, while the village government utilizes the village information system, WhatsApp Group, and direct meetings to manage and convey data.

Field findings show that, in general, the flow of information and coordination has been running quite well. The Head of Sumberrejo Village stated that information from BPS and the district is generally conveyed clearly through coordination meetings and WhatsApp groups. However, sudden changes to the socialization schedule require village officials to adapt quickly in implementing the program.

A similar view was expressed by the Secretary of Balen Village, who assessed that coordination with the district has been running relatively well. However, he highlighted the delay in information from the district government, which affected the village's readiness in carrying out data collection tasks. In addition, additional technical training is still needed so that the data submitted by the village can be more accurate and complete in accordance with BPS standards.

Meanwhile, the Dander Village Data Team revealed that they regularly attend coordination meetings at the district level. However, horizontal communication between villages is still limited. Changes in data formats or new requests from BPS are often only communicated via WhatsApp, requiring intensive monitoring by the village data team.

Based on the analysis results, the information flow and coordination of the Desa Cantik Program have been designed systematically and utilize a multi-channel approach, including coordination meetings, face-to-face socialization, and digital media. This approach supports the smooth distribution of information from the district to the village level. However, Simbolon et al. (2022) research shows that there are still obstacles, including delays in information flow, especially at the distribution stage from the regency to the district and village levels.

The coordination obstacles found include differences in priorities and timing between institutions, which cause sudden schedule changes, limited human resource capacity at the district and village levels, and variations in information technology capabilities and infrastructure between villages. These conditions have an impact on the effectiveness of communication and the readiness of villages to respond to technical policy changes.

The coordination obstacles identified include differences in priorities and timing between agencies, which cause sudden schedule changes; limited human resource capacity at the district and village levels; and variations in information technology capabilities and infrastructure between villages. These conditions have an impact on the effectiveness of communication and the readiness of villages to respond to changes in technical policies.

Thus, although the flow of information and coordination of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency has a clear structure and is running relatively well, the challenges of implementation in the field still need serious attention. In line with Edward's III (1980) theory, synchronization and coordination across bureaucracies are absolute prerequisites for policies to move beyond the administrative level and be effectively and sustainably implemented at the village level.

c. Evaluation of Communication Effectiveness

An evaluation of the effectiveness of communication in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency shows that communication is a central factor that directly influences the success of the program. The results of empirical data analysis and interviews show that the level of understanding of village officials and the community, the smooth flow of information, and the degree of participation in statistical data management are highly dependent on the quality of communication established between policy makers and implementers in the field.

The head of the Bojonegoro Regency BPS emphasized that the essence of the Desa Cantik Program lies not only in the technical aspects of data collection, but also in efforts to increase the capacity of village officials and foster a culture of love for statistics at the local level. Effective communication is a key prerequisite for ensuring that these objectives are fully understood by village officials and appreciated by the community, particularly in terms of supporting data-based development planning and poverty alleviation.

The results of a comparative study conducted by Isnaini & Khikmah (2025) in Kendal Regency reinforce these findings. More than 75% of respondents expressed satisfaction with the socialization process, village participation, and BPS support. However, the study also noted that there were still obstacles in terms of coordination and community involvement, indicating that the effectiveness of communication is not only determined by the frequency of socialization, but also by the quality of interaction and continuity of information.

Based on field surveys in Sumberrejo, Balen, and Dander villages (Utomo, 2025), the effectiveness of the Desa Cantik Program communication showed variations in achievement between indicators. Understanding of the program's objectives was achieved by 62% of respondents, indicating that the majority of village officials have recognized the direction of the policy, although there are still a significant number who do not fully understand the substance of the program. This condition has the potential to cause differences in the quality of implementation and data management between villages.

The aspects of timeliness and completeness of information achieved a relatively lower score of 58%. This finding indicates that delays in information delivery and sudden changes in instructions are still issues in the policy communication process. This situation has an impact on the readiness of villages to respond to data requests or technical adjustments from BPS.

In terms of the quality of the socialization material, only 54% of respondents considered the material easy to understand. This shows that the communication content still tends to be technical and has not been fully adapted to the diverse educational backgrounds of village officials. Although discussion forums and question-and-answer sessions have been facilitated with an achievement rate of 60%, their effectiveness is considered suboptimal in bridging this gap in understanding.

Access to communication media, both face-to-face and digital, is fairly good with an achievement rate of 68%. The use of WhatsApp groups, face-to-face meetings, and village digital media helps to expand the reach of information. However, the effectiveness of these media is still limited by variations in information technology capabilities between villages and limitations in digital infrastructure, especially for certain community groups.

Coordination between levels of government is one of the main weaknesses in communication effectiveness, with an achievement rate of 55%. This low figure reflects the continuing obstacles to synchronization between the regency, district, and village governments. This is reinforced by the results of interviews with Sumberrejo Village officials and the Head of Dander Village, who revealed frequent changes to the coordination schedule and sudden delivery of information, thereby hampering the effectiveness of the village apparatus.

Community participation in data collection, which only reached 57%, shows that program communication has not been fully able to encourage the active involvement of all residents. This low participation is inseparable from the community's limited understanding of the direct benefits of village statistical data, as well as the lack of a participatory and contextual communication approach.

Overall, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the Desa Cantik Program communication in Bojonegoro Regency shows significant progress, especially in the provision of communication channels and the initial understanding of village officials. However, there is still substantial room for improvement, particularly in simplifying communication materials, improving the timeliness of information delivery, strengthening inter-institutional coordination, and increasing community participation. In line with Edward III's (1980) policy implementation theory, improvements in communication are key to ensuring that the Desa Cantik Program runs more effectively and has a real impact on data-driven village development.

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Overall, communication indicators in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency show that the policy delivery process has a clear structure, is carried out repeatedly, and utilizes various communication channels, both face-to-face and digital. Socialization mechanisms through training for village officials, outreach to the community, and support from modern communication media have helped to increase initial understanding of the program's objectives and benefits. The flow of information and coordination across institutions—from BPS, regency government, district, to village—has basically been running quite well and has enabled policies to be translated into village data management practices. However, communication effectiveness has not been fully optimized due to obstacles such as relatively technical socialization materials, delays and inconsistencies in information, and cross-bureaucratic coordination that is not yet fully synchronized. These conditions have resulted in varying levels of understanding among village officials, limited community participation, and disparities in the quality of implementation between villages. In line with George C. Edward's (1980) policy implementation theory, these findings confirm that the success of the Desa Cantik Program is largely determined by the ability of policy communication to convey messages clearly, timely, consistently, and contextually. Therefore, strengthening the quality of communication is a key prerequisite for improving program effectiveness and the sustainability of data-driven village development.

2) Resources

Human Resources

In Edward III's (1980) policy implementation theory, human resources are one of the main determinants of public policy success. Edward emphasizes that policies will not be effective without the support of an adequate number of implementers with the appropriate competencies and the willingness to implement the policies consistently. In the context of the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik) in Bojonegoro Regency, the quality of human resources is a crucial factor because this program requires technical skills in collecting, processing, analyzing, and reporting village statistical data.

Based on a 2024 field survey in three implementing villages—Sumberrejo, Balen, and Dander—there were significant variations in the number of village officials, the intensity of training, and the level of statistical understanding. The empirical data is summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Number of Officials Who Participated in Training

Village	Number of Officials	Training/Year	Understanding of Statistics (%)	Officials Experiences Difficulties
Sumberrejo	25	3	70	5
Balen	20	2	60	7
Dander	18	2	55	6

Source: Data processed by researchers from the Bojonegoro Regency BPS Official Report 2023-2024 (2025)

The data shows that Sumberrejo Village has the highest number of officials and training intensity compared to other villages. This condition is directly proportional to the level of statistical understanding of officials, which reaches 70%. However, there are still around 20% of officials who report difficulties in managing statistical data, indicating that increasing human resource capacity does not only depend on the frequency of training but also on the effectiveness of methods and the level of individual adaptation.

Conversely, Balen and Dander Villages, which have fewer officials and lower training intensity, show relatively lower levels of statistical understanding, at 60% and 55% respectively. This has resulted in a higher number of officials experiencing technical difficulties, particularly in the use of village statistics applications and the digital data entry process.

Human resource competence in the Desa Cantik Program is not only measured by participation in formal training, but also by the ability to apply statistical knowledge in daily work practices. The head of the Bojonegoro Regency BPS emphasized that the mental readiness, willingness to learn, and courage of village officials to adapt to new technologies are important prerequisites for the realization of village independence in statistical data management.

Field findings show that the training provided by BPS has increased the confidence of some village officials, especially in the use of statistical applications. However, the limited computer literacy of some officials means that work processes are often carried out collectively. In Balen Village, for example, data entry is often carried out jointly by several officials to overcome individual technical limitations. Meanwhile, in Dander Village, officials emphasized the need for more intensive practice-based training, especially for new members of the data management team.

In addition to formal training, informal mentoring mechanisms and internal knowledge sharing have become quite effective adaptive strategies. Younger village officials or those with better digital literacy often serve as informal facilitators for their colleagues. This collaborative pattern helps to overcome limitations in the number and competence of human resources, especially in villages with limited human resources.

However, this study also identified several major obstacles in the human resources sub-indicator, including low digital and statistical literacy among senior officials, high administrative workloads that limit learning time, and a lack of courage to try new technologies. These obstacles have the potential to hamper the effectiveness and sustainability of the Desa Cantik Program's implementation.

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In response, BPS and local governments consistently organize ongoing training, provide direct technical assistance to villages, and strengthen collaborative data management teams. This approach has proven to help improve the adaptation of village human resources to the increasingly complex demands of statistical data management.

Overall, the human resources sub-indicator shows that the success of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency is largely determined by the adequacy of the number of officials, their level of statistical competence, and their active participation in training and continuous learning. Strengthening human resource capacity through formal training, intensive mentoring, and internal knowledge-sharing mechanisms is the main foundation for improving the quality of village data and the sustainability of evidence-based development at the local level.

a. Budget Resources

In the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency, budget resources are a strategic element that determines the sustainability and effectiveness of program implementation. The availability and smooth flow of funding has a direct impact on the implementation of training for officials, the provision of supporting facilities, and technical assistance for village statistical data management.

The main source of funding for the Desa Cantik Program comes from the Village Fund (DD) allocated through the State Budget (APBN), the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBDes), and district government support in the form of Special Financial Assistance (BKK). The Village Fund is a vital component because it finances most village activities, including data-based programs. However, the disbursement of the Village Fund is carried out in stages and requires the completion of accountability reports as a prerequisite for the sustainability of disbursement.

Selain Dana Desa, APBDes juga mengalokasikan anggaran khusus untuk pemberdayaan masyarakat. In addition to the Village Fund, the APBDes also allocates a special budget for community empowerment and strengthening the capacity of village officials, especially in statistical data management. The Bojonegoro Regency Government also provides support through Special Financial Assistance (BKK) directed at village development priorities, information system development, and statistical training.

Based on an analysis of the 2025 budget data, the allocation of funds for the Desa Cantik Program at the village level ranges from IDR 50 million to IDR 100 million per village per year. The budget is used for apparatus training, procurement of technological infrastructure, assistance, and program administration. Details of the estimated budget allocation are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Budget Allocation for the Desa Cantik Program

Description	Budget
Training and Socialization (speaker fees, meals, materials)	IDR 15-25 million
Procurement of Facilities and Infrastructure (computers, modems, internet)	IDR 20-40 million
Assistance and Monitoring (fees, transportation)	IDR 10-20 million
Program Administration (documentation, reports, communication)	IDR 5-15 million
Total	IDR 50-100 million/year

Source: Data processed by researchers from the APBDes and BPS official reports of Bojonegoro Regency 2023-2025 (2025)

Although the budget allocation is relatively adequate, its management at the village level still faces administrative obstacles. All use of funds must be reported through the OMSPAN system as a condition for the next stage of disbursement. Villages with limited administrative capacity risk delays or even suspension of fund disbursement, as happened in Drokilo Village, which failed to disburse Village Funds in 2025 due to incomplete accountability reports from the previous year.

The Head of the Community and Village Empowerment Agency (PMD) of Bojonegoro Regency explained that these obstacles were not caused by a lack of budget, but rather by limited administrative management capacity at the village level:

"We have provided intensive assistance with administration and the use of Village Funds. However, the limited capacity of village officials and administrative staff has made it difficult for some villages to meet the disbursement requirements, resulting in the suspension of funds and the delay of programs."

Conversely, villages with better budget management capacity are able to utilize the funds optimally. The Head of Sumberrejo Village said that the budget allocation from the Village Fund and APBDes was used to improve the competence of the apparatus and provide data management support tools:

"We took the budget allocation for the Desa Cantik Program from the Village Fund and APBDes. These funds were used to train village officials and purchase computer equipment, which greatly helped the data management process."

Thus, budget resources indicate that the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency is supported by relatively sufficient and diverse funding sources. However, the effectiveness of budget utilization is highly dependent on the capacity of village administration and financial management. Therefore, strengthening the capacity of village officials in budget management and financial reporting is a key factor in ensuring that financial support can be utilized optimally and the program can run sustainably.

Overall, the resource indicators in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency show that the success of the program is largely determined by the synergy between the quality of human resources and the adequacy of budget resources. In terms of human resources, variations in the number of officials, the intensity of training, and the level of statistical understanding

have a direct implication on the village's ability to manage data accurately and sustainably, where villages with more intensive training tend to show better understanding despite still facing limitations in digital literacy and technological adaptation. Meanwhile, from a budgetary perspective, the availability of relatively adequate funding through the Village Fund, APBDes, and district government support has enabled the implementation of training, procurement of supporting facilities, and technical assistance, but the effectiveness of its utilization is highly dependent on administrative capacity and financial management at the village level. Thus, in line with Edward III's (1980) view, the successful implementation of the Desa Cantik Program requires not only sufficient quantitative resources but also competent implementing capacity and an accountable budget management system to achieve the goal of strengthening evidence-based village data governance in an optimal and sustainable manner.

3) Disposition

Commitment and Motivation of Villages

In Edward's (1980) policy implementation theory, the disposition of implementers—which includes attitudes, commitment, and motivation—is a key factor in determining whether policies are implemented consistently and effectively. In the context of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency, the disposition of village officials is reflected in the sincerity of the village head, village officials, and data management team in making statistics-based programs a part of village development priorities.

The commitment of village officials can be seen from their active participation in training, direct involvement in the data collection process, and the continuity of statistical data management at the village level. This commitment is reinforced by local government policies that place data-based programs as a strategic agenda in the 2025–2029 Bojonegoro Regency Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD). This support was manifested, among other things, through seminars and briefings organized by the Bojonegoro Regency Community and Village Empowerment Agency (DPMD) in 2025, which were attended by 108 village heads from 25 districts and discussed the management of data and technology-based programs.

The motivation of village officials comes from both internal and external factors. Internally, motivation is influenced by a sense of social responsibility and awareness of the importance of data as the basis for village development planning. Externally, motivation is strengthened by recognition from the district government, ongoing technical assistance, and encouragement from the community, which expects more targeted village development. This is reflected in the statement of the village head who said:

“We are committed to implementing the Desa Cantik Program because we see its direct benefits in village development planning. The training and assistance we have received have made us even more motivated to manage data properly.”

In line with this, village officials in Balen emphasized that work motivation has increased due to appreciation and support from all levels of government, even though the challenge of workload is still felt:

“Our motivation has increased because there is recognition from the district government and encouragement from the community who want targeted development. Even though we are sometimes busy with other things, we still try to prioritize data management in accordance with the program.”

In general, the level of commitment and motivation of village officials in implementing the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency is relatively high and is an important asset for the program's sustainability. However, administrative workloads and limited resources have the potential to weaken motivation if not balanced with adequate assistance, supervision, and reward mechanisms. Thus, the commitment and motivation of the villages demonstrate that strong implementation not only ensures the program runs routinely but also opens up space for innovation and the optimal use of statistical data for sustainable village development.

a. Perception of Program Benefits

Perception of benefits is an important part of the disposition of implementers and the community because it determines the level of acceptance, support, and sustainability of policy implementation. In the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency, the perception of benefits is reflected in the extent to which village officials and the community feel the real impact of the program in data management and village development planning.

Based on the 2024–2025 report from the Bojonegoro Regency Government and BPS, the Desa Cantik Program is perceived as a strategic means to increase the capacity of village officials in statistical data management, strengthen evidence-based development planning, and accelerate the handling of socio-economic issues such as poverty and improving community welfare. The head of the Bojonegoro Regency BPS emphasized that the program's objectives are not only technical in nature but also aim to foster a culture of love for statistics so that data becomes an integral part of village governance.

The concrete benefits felt by the villages include increased ease of program evaluation and data-based decision-making, thereby strengthening the accountability and transparency of village management. This is reinforced by the results of a survey conducted in early 2025 in the villages of Sumberrejo, Balen, and Dander, which showed that 78% of village officials felt an increase in their data management capabilities, while 64% of the community stated that they felt the benefits of the program. Other aspects such as planning accuracy, transparency, acceleration of social assistance distribution, and increased community participation also received positive assessments.

The survey findings were reinforced by in-depth interviews. The Head of Sumberrejo Village stated that the availability of accurate data facilitated development planning and the determination of priority recipients of assistance. Balen Village officials highlighted

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increased community trust due to improved data transparency, while Dander Village residents acknowledged improvements in access to information and the accuracy of social assistance distribution.

Analytically, the relatively positive perception of benefits indicates that the Desa Cantik Program has succeeded in increasing public trust and village capacity in statistical data management. This perception also encourages community participation and strengthens more accountable village governance. However, there are still some people who have not fully felt the direct benefits of the program. Therefore, strengthening socialization and more inclusive assistance is still needed so that the perceived benefits can be felt evenly and become the foundation for the sustainable implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency.

b. Local Leadership and Initiative

The results of the study on the sub-indicators of local leadership and initiative show that the successful implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency is greatly influenced by the active role of village heads and local leaders in encouraging program implementation, developing innovations in village data management, and mobilizing community participation. Responsive and innovative leadership is a distinguishing factor between villages in maximizing the utilization of the Desa Cantik Program.

These findings are in line with the research by Rohmah et al. (2025), which shows that village heads with a transformational leadership style—open, empathetic, and visionary—are able to increase community participation and encourage local innovation. The study emphasizes that village heads not only play an administrative role but also act as agents of change through various community empowerment initiatives and the use of technology.

The results of the survey and evaluation of the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in three implementing villages during the 2024–2025 period show a relatively strong leadership role at the village level, as summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Local Leadership and Initiative Percentages

Local Leadership and Initiative Indicators	Sumberrejo (%)	Balen (%)	Dander (%)
Village heads actively promote the program	85	78	80
Innovation in data processing	70	70	72
Encouraged community participation	90	88	70
Formation of a data processing team	Yes	Yes	Yes

Source: Data processed by researchers (2025)

The data shows that village heads in the three villages generally play an active role in promoting the program, facilitating innovation in data management, and increasing community participation. This leadership role is reinforced by the results of interviews with key actors. The Head of Sumberrejo Village also emphasized the role of leadership in building a sustainable data management system through the formation of a special team and regular evaluations:

“I actively promote the formation of a village data team, often holding evaluation meetings and internal training sessions. This is our effort to ensure that data management runs smoothly and community participation continues to increase.”

Meanwhile, a community leader in Balen Village assessed that the openness and creativity of the village head are important factors in encouraging citizen involvement:

“Our village head is very creative, often inviting us to participate in programs and providing training on the importance of data. He is also open to feedback from citizens.”

These findings show that visionary and innovative leadership can increase the motivation of village officials and community participation in the Desa Cantik Program. Local initiatives such as the formation of data management teams, independent training, and the use of digital technology are key factors in the success of the program at the village level. This reinforces the view that responsive and progressive local leaders can optimize village resources and strengthen data-based development governance.

Thus, local leadership and initiatives play a strategic role in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency. Village heads who are active, innovative, and able to mobilize the community have proven to contribute significantly to improving the quality of village statistical data management. Therefore, strengthening leadership capacity and providing space for local initiatives needs to be the focus of program development so that its positive impact can be replicated in other villages.

Overall, disposition indicators in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency show that the attitudes, commitment, and orientation of implementers at the village level are relatively strong and conducive to the success of the program. The commitment and motivation of village officials are reflected in their active participation in training, continuous involvement in statistical data management, and willingness to make data-based programs a part of village development priorities, which is reinforced by regional policy support through the RPJMD (Regional Medium-Term Development Plan). Positive perceptions of benefits—both among village officials and the community—reinforce this disposition, as valid data is perceived to improve the accuracy of planning, transparency, accountability, and public trust in village administration. On the other hand, local leadership and initiative serve as catalysts that drive collective disposition, where active, innovative, and open village heads and local leaders are able to encourage the formation of data management teams, develop technology-based innovations, and increase community participation. Despite still facing challenges in the form of administrative workloads and resource constraints, the combination of

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the commitment of officials, the perception of tangible benefits, and responsive local leadership shows that the disposition of the Desa Cantik Program implementers has formed a strong social and institutional foundation for the sustainability and optimization of data-based village development in Bojonegoro Regency.

4) Bureaucrat Structure

Mechanisms and Operational Procedures

The bureaucratic structure of village administration in Bojonegoro Regency has been systematically regulated through Regional Regulations and Regent Regulations that provide clarity on the hierarchy, division of tasks, and responsibilities of village officials. This regulatory framework is an important basis for the implementation of village programs, including the Desa Cantik Program (Cinta Statistik), so that policy implementation can be measured and in accordance with established standards.

Structurally, the village administration consists of the Village Head as the highest leader, the Village Secretariat which coordinates administrative and planning matters, the Hamlet Head as the liaison at the regional level, and the Section Heads who handle government, welfare, and public services. The division of tasks and functions of the village apparatus is reflected in the following table.

Table 6. Division of Tasks of Village Officials

Position	Main Duties
Village Head	Leading and coordinating all village administration and development activities
Village Secretary	Assisting the Village Head in administrative and public service matters
Head of Administration and General Affairs	Handling general administration, equipment, and archives
Head of Finance	Managing village finances, budgets, and financial reporting
Head of Planning	Developing village development plans and activities
Hamlet Head	Coordinating activities at the hamlet level
Head of Government	Managing village government administration
Head of Welfare	Managing social and community welfare programs
Head of Services	Handling public services and population administration

Source: Bojonegoro Regency Regulation Number 6 of 2006 (2025)

In the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program, the operational mechanism is carried out through structured stages. The planning stage is carried out through the preparation of the Village Government Work Plan (RKPD_{Des}) by prioritizing statistical data management, which involves the Village Secretariat and the Head of Planning. In the implementation stage, the village data management team, consisting of village officials and cadres, collects, processes, and verifies data using official applications facilitated by BPS, with monitoring by the relevant Section Head. The monitoring and evaluation stage is carried out by the Village Head and Village Secretary through coordination meetings and field supervision, while the reporting stage is carried out periodically to the District and district BPS through the village information system with accountability supervision by the Head of Finance.

Based on an internal survey conducted by the Village Government and BPS Bojonegoro in 2024, the level of regularity of operational mechanisms and satisfaction with procedures is quite high in villages implementing the Desa Cantik Program, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Regularity of the Desa Cantik Operational Mechanism

Village	Structured Operational Mechanism (%)	Satisfaction with Procedures (%)
Sumberrejo	85	80
Balen	78	75
Dander	73	70

Source: BPS of Bojonegoro Regency 2025 (2025)

These findings were reinforced by interviews with village officials, in which the Secretary of Sumberrejo Village stated that all stages of the Desa Cantik Program had been carried out in accordance with SOPs, including specific SOPs for data collection activities. The Head of the Dander Village Services Section revealed that despite communication challenges between departments, coordination was still maintained through regular meetings and online communication media. Meanwhile, the Data Operator of Balen Village emphasized that the use of the official BPS application, which is integrated with the village information system, has made data management and reporting more structured.

Overall, the mechanisms and operational procedures of village administration in Bojonegoro Regency have supported the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program through a clear division of functions, the application of SOPs, and an integrated monitoring and reporting system. This structure not only reinforces the role of village officials, but also strengthens the principles of accountability and effectiveness in the management of village statistical data.

a. Inter-Institutional Coordination

Inter-institutional coordination is a crucial aspect in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency because it determines the effectiveness of cooperation, information exchange, and synchronization of actions between government agencies from the regency, district, to village levels, including community institutions. Good coordination ensures that the program runs smoothly, avoids policy overlaps, and optimizes the use of resources.

Conceptually, coordination is the process of harmonizing various efforts to move harmoniously towards a common goal (Muharsono et al., 2023; Siagian, 2008). In the context of the Desa Cantik Program, coordination plays an important role in data integration, cross-sector policy synchronization, and the resolution of technical and administrative issues. Cooperation between regional apparatus, Bakorwil, districts, village governments, and community institutions encourages more focused and sustainable data-driven village development (Alkadafi et al., 2025; Muhtar et al., 2022).

The Regional Coordination Agency (Bakorwil) II Bojonegoro acts as the main coordinator that facilitates communication between the district government, relevant agencies, districts, and villages. The coordination mechanism is implemented through regular coordination meetings, field visits and monitoring by Bakorwil and DPMD, as well as the use of digital media such as WhatsApp groups as a means of rapid communication. In addition, coordination forums that produce mutual agreements form the basis for program implementation, although they are not yet accompanied by formal sanctions.

The results of an internal survey conducted by the Bojonegoro Regency Government in 2024 show that coordination between institutions is considered quite effective. The level of satisfaction with the smooth communication between agencies reached 82%, with an average coordination frequency of 1-2 times per month through direct meetings and digital media. The effectiveness of cross-sectoral problem solving was recorded at 75%, while the availability of accurate information reached 78% and the active participation of village community institutions was 70%.

These findings indicate that the use of various coordination channels, both face-to-face and digital, has supported the smooth implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency. The challenges that still need to be addressed are mainly related to the consistency of follow-up on coordination results and strengthening cross-regional cooperation. Thus, coordination between institutions has a strategic role in connecting all stakeholders and ensuring that the Desa Cantik Program runs harmoniously, accountably, and sustainably.

b. Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation in the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program serve as a control and learning mechanism to ensure that the program runs according to its objectives. Monitoring is carried out to monitor the implementation of data collection, processing, and reporting of statistical data on a regular basis, while evaluation is used to assess the effectiveness of the program in improving the capacity of village officials and the use of data as a basis for development planning. The existence of monitoring and evaluation enables early identification of technical obstacles, resource constraints, and gaps between targets and achievements at the village level.

Based on the monitoring results, the participation of village officials in training and mentoring activities was relatively high, although there were still limitations in terms of the timeliness of reporting, data validity, and community participation in the data collection process. These findings were reinforced by interviews with the Sumberrejo District Village Assistance Team, who stated that monitoring was carried out routinely every quarter through field visits and technical assistance.

They emphasized that the monitoring results form the basis for the preparation of evaluation reports submitted to BPS and DPMD as follow-up material for the program. Meanwhile, the Head of Dander Village revealed that the evaluation process helps the village government identify weaknesses in data management and encourages more targeted improvements.

Overall, the monitoring and evaluation sub-indicators show that the Desa Cantik Program has a fairly systematic and participatory oversight mechanism. Monitoring and evaluation not only serve as administrative control tools, but also as reflective instruments to improve data quality, apparatus capacity, and community involvement. With consistent utilization of evaluation results, monitoring and evaluation become an important foundation for the sustainability and strengthening of statistical data management at the village level.

Based on the results of research on bureaucratic structure indicators within the framework of Edward III's (1980) policy implementation, it can be concluded that the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program in Bojonegoro Regency has been supported by clear mechanisms and operational procedures, relatively effective inter-agency coordination, and a structured monitoring and evaluation system. The clear division of tasks among village officials and the implementation of SOPs enable each stage of the program—from planning and implementation to reporting—to be carried out in a measurable and accountable manner. Inter-agency coordination facilitated by the Regional Coordination Agency (Bakorwil), relevant agencies, districts, and village governments through various face-to-face and digital channels has been able to support policy synchronization and information exchange, although follow-up consistency still needs to be strengthened. Meanwhile, periodic monitoring and evaluation serve not only as administrative control tools but also as learning tools to improve data quality, village apparatus capacity, and community participation. Overall, the established bureaucratic structure provides a sufficiently strong foundation for the implementation of the Desa Cantik Program, although strengthening cross-sectoral coordination and optimizing the utilization of evaluation results are

still needed to make the bureaucratic structure more adaptive and responsive to the dynamics of data-driven village development needs.

4. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the implementation of the Desa Cantik (Cinta Statistik) Program in Bojonegoro Regency has generally progressed well, supported by clear communication channels between BPS, local government, and village-level actors, adequate institutional and technological resources, and a positive disposition among implementers who demonstrate commitment to improving village data governance. The existence of standardized operating procedures, structured coordination mechanisms, and routine monitoring and evaluation has strengthened bureaucratic effectiveness and accountability in program implementation. The findings also indicate that leadership at the village level plays a significant role in mobilizing participation and encouraging innovation in data management practices, although disparities in human resource capacity and data literacy remain evident across villages. Despite these achievements, challenges persist in ensuring data accuracy, sustaining inter-agency coordination, and optimizing the use of statistical data for strategic development planning. This research is limited by its qualitative design and focus on three villages, which may not fully represent broader implementation dynamics across Bojonegoro Regency. Moreover, the study does not quantitatively assess the impact of improved data management on development outcomes. Future research is therefore recommended to employ mixed-method or longitudinal approaches, expand the scope of analysis to include more villages, and examine the long-term influence of the Desa Cantik Program on evidence-based policymaking, budgeting effectiveness, and socio-economic development at the village level.

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